

F-16 DEPOT AUTOMATIC TEST EQUIPMENT

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ABSTRACT

General Dynamics Corporation, Fort Worth Division (GD/FW) is currently developing the F-16 depot level Automatic Test Equipment (ATE) system under the direction of the F-16 System Program Office (SPO) located at Wright-Patterson Air Force Base, Ohio. Existing design testers are being extensively utilized through update and improvement modifications, with the vast majority of the development work concentrated in the Test Packages (Interface Test Adapters (ITAs) and test programs). This paper describes the acquisition management techniques used and the various ATE and software development aids selected to date. The test package development effort is described. Our approach to supporting EPROM/PROM ICs is presented. Configuration management is discussed. Finally, a look at the program future is given.

ACQUISITION MANAGEMENT

The F-16 prime contractor, General Dynamics/Fort Worth (GD/FW) Division, has overall responsibility for the F-16 depot support equipment program with the advice, consent and direction of the F-16 SPO. Initial studies were accomplished in early 1976 to determine what aircraft components were economically repairable through the Optimum Repair Level Analysis (ORLA). A list of aircraft electronic assemblies, primarily Shop Replaceable Units (SRUs), was drawn up for consideration of ATE applicability. (To this day this list of aircraft assemblies to be tested on depot ATE is continually changing.) GD/FW also supported ATE selection studies, Automatic Test Program Generation (ATPG) selection studies and the generation of various plans and documentation specifications. Figure 1 shows the process of identifying the Support Equipment (SE) to be used for aircraft or aircraft support equipment (SE for SE) support and how the AF contracts with GD/FW for this equipment. The Resident Integrated Logistics Support Agency (RILSA) is an Air Force organization which reviews the ORLA information on each candidate repairable item and makes the final repairable support requirement determination. A Support Equipment Recommendation Data (SERD) is a description of

the specific support requirement and a recommended piece of support equipment, including the price. The preliminary SERD is the same as the SERD except that it is unpriced. For example, one SERD was submitted for the analog test station and one is submitted for each ITA and test program combination.

Figure 1. Depot Support Equipment Identification Process

Air Force Logistics Command (AFLC) has recently decided to consolidate at the Air Logistics Center (ALC) located at Hill Air Force Base, Ogden, Utah, all depot ATE used to test F-16 peculiar avionics. Justification for this shift of workload from the normal Technical Repair Center (TRC) concept included money savings of consolidation and European Participating Government (EPG) desires to have a consolidated ATE depot.

The F-16 depot ATE program is attempting to implement the intent of Air Force Regulation 800-14, Management of Computer Resources in

Systems. We (GD/FW and the AF) have written an extensive Computer Program Development Plan for the depot ATE. This plan delineates in detail the development process for test packages and new development ATE station software. Detailed requirements for test packages are included. The plan also provides good AF visibility into the development effort. The AF is also writing a Computer Resources Integrated Support Plan (CRISP) which will describe how we plan to support ATE software after it is delivered. This support includes: 1) the ability to repair, 2) retarget to a different tester and 3) modify ATE software if the SRU is modified. All of these efforts insure that a good product will be delivered to the depot initially and that the ALCs will be able to support it organically after delivery on a long term basis. We are also treating the vast majority of our software as configured items (Computer Program Configured Items). Good Test Package/ATE documentation is being provided. In short, we are giving the software the visibility and attention comparable with the hardware and necessary for a successful development effort.

ATE

The F-16 SPO recognized the many pitfalls of developing new ATE from the very outset. Both the intermediate shop and the depot ATE teams examined existing equipment to determine if it could be used. From the initial ORLAs a first cut at stimuli and measurement requirements was derived for the F-16 avionic SRUs. These were matched against the various existing AF inventory ATE stations using the San Antonio ATE Data Bank and ATE vendor data. The F-16 Depot ATE Selection Team was formed consisting of GD/FW, F-16 SPO and ALC personnel. The team determined that existing AF inventory testers should be utilized to test all of the F-16 avionic SRUs. After technical trade-off studies and much discussion, the team selected the following three testers by mid 1977: 1) the Honeywell ADTS analog station used on the F-15 program, 2) the Hewlett Packard COMETS microwave station used on the F-111 program and 3) the Texas Instruments DTS digital station used on the F-4 program. We are also purchasing two Honeywell Mini-DEMS analog test program development stations.

We all recognized that some modifications/ updating would be desirable and more copies of these stations would be procured. ITA complexity would also probably be greater using existing testers. However, it is strongly believed that through the use of existing stations a great deal of maintenance, training and development money is saved.

We were aware of some stimuli and measurement capability shortcomings in the stations prior to selection. Since station selection we have become aware of other problems along those lines. Actually, this is typical of most ATE development programs and not due to the selection of existing testers. Many of these shortcomings

were similar for a number of SRUs. Instead of incorporating this kind of capability into all of the ITAs we decided to add what we call ancillary equipment to the stations.

The F-16 Aircraft was a complex avionics system utilizing a Mil-STD-1553 MUX Bus. This bus works at 2-4 MHz. The LRUs tied into the bus all have Input/Output SRUs to tie into the bus. Many of these SRUs must be tested at their normal operating speed (2-4 MHz). The TI-960 digital tester does not have this capability. We therefore have added a Serial Word Generator to generate SRU inputs and a Data Storage Unit to catch SRU highspeed outputs. These are both connected to the ITA and are loaded and controlled via normal ATLAS test program statements. We believe some 20-30 digital SRUs will utilize one or the other or both of these devices resulting in significant ITA complexity reduction. Consideration is also being given to some sort of SRU heater to help in detecting "soft" or intermittent type failures.

A small accessory kit consisting of probes and voltage offset devices is being added to the analog station. The microwave station does not have the capability to make required phase noise measurements. An ancillary piece of equipment similar to what Westinghouse (F-16 radar vendor) uses in manufacturing is being considered to provide the capability needed to test some 4-5 radar SRUs.

AUTOMATIC TEST PROGRAM GENERATION

One of the "lessons learned" of the F-15 program is the significance of Automatic Test Program Generation (ATPG) for both initial generation of digital SRU test programs and later test program organic support. The AF allowed approximately seven different ATPG systems to be used in the generation of F-15 SRU test programs, and now it is having a difficult time providing AF organic support for those test programs. Procuring all those ATPG systems is prohibitively expensive and even impossible in some cases due to ATPG product line discontinuance. The F-16 SPO decided to attempt to standardize on an ATPG system to be used on as many of the F-16 digital SRUs as possible. It was recognized that some small percentage of the digital SRUs would not be ATPG applicable due to circuit design and use of unmodeled LSI circuits. It now appears that some 15-20% of our digital SRUs will not be ATPG applicable. Initially GD/FW would use the ATPG system for the development of the test programs (1978-1980). As more and more test programs were completed and shipped to the ALC we would transfer ATPG capability to the ALC (1980-1982). This transfer of capability would be accomplished via a modem/ phone remote tie-in if one large ATPG system was selected, or as a shipment of one ATPG unit if a multiple small ATPG system was selected. At the end of the test program development effort the entire ATPG would be shipped to the ALC for their use in supporting the test programs.

As in the ATE selection, we had a strong desire to use an existing system. We had no desire to develop a new ATPG system and had reason to believe this would not be necessary. Delivery of source code was desirable but not mandatory. The F-16 SPO, GD/FW and the ALCs participated in the ATPG selection.

GD/FW owned two older ATPG system in-house: 1) GenRad CAPS VII and 2) Digitest D-2 LASAR. GD/FW attempted to generate test patterns for two SRUs using these systems and determined that they would not be adequate for the F-16 program. After much discussion we selected 10 ATPG potential sources for an "ATPG flyoff". These 10 vendors were: 1) Digitest, 2) Hewlett Packard, 3) RRC International, 4) PRD, 5) Pacific Applied Sciences, 6) Micro, 7) Data Science, 8) Computer Software Analysts, 9) Dunbar System and 10) Grumman Aerospace. After five of these companies responded to our RFP we elected to hire four of them to develop test patterns for two SRUs. The four vendors were: 1) Digitest, 2) Hewlett Packard, 3) Pacific Applied Sciences and 4) Grumman Aerospace. The two SRUs were the Zero Frequency Detector SRU out of the Westinghouse Radar system and the Digital Input/Output SRU out of the Delco Magic Fire Control Computer. Component count and other component information was provided but not SRU schematics prior to the "flyoff" to allow pricing of the test pattern generation effort. A relatively high fault detection percentage of 98% was required. Schedule constraints were also made. The two SRUs were chosen to be representative of the F-16 digital SRUs, composed primarily of Medium Scale Integration (MSI) circuits with no LSI circuits.

GD/FW supplied SRU schematics and sent an engineer to each of the four ATPG vendors to monitor test pattern development progress. The F-16 SPO also visited each ATPG vendor during this effort. All relevant objective data, such as machine time, manhours, fault detection/isolation percentage, etc. were carefully recorded by the GD/FW engineer. Subjective things such as degree of difficulty in using the system, etc. were also monitored. In order to verify the ATPG vendor fault detection/isolation percentages a common digital simulator was selected and all patterns run against it. The details of the above vendor selection study are published in a report, General Dynamics Document Number 16PR687. The results of the study were that the D-4 LASAR software system was the optimum system for the F-16 program. Further analysis resulted in selecting the Scientific Machines Corporation SMC-3110 multiprocessor midi-computer system to host the D-4 LASAR software system. The selection was basically complete by mid-1977.

GD/FW is developing additional software for the system to provide the AF complete configuration management of the digital test programs, the capability to generate certain documentation and in general improve the ALCs ability to support the software after release to the field. Figure 2 shows how the ATPG System and the digital test station relate.

Figure 2. ATPG/Digital Test Station Relationship

RADAR ANTENNA/RADOME TEST RANGES

The F-16 ORLA indicates that it is cost effective from a Life Cycle Cost point of view to develop the capability to extensively repair F-16 radar antennas and nose radomes. Both of these components are state-of-the-art high value items and will require sophisticated test systems. Initial studies included examining existing outdoor test ranges which have historically been used to test these equipments. No existing range could meet our stiff accuracy or workload requirements. We then investigated a compact indoor type range which would eliminate the weather limitations of outdoor ranges. When GD/FW concluded that such a range was feasible we elected to initiate SERD development. We are about to initiate Radome Test Range development and will start Radar Antenna Test Range development by early next year. We will probably invest some 20-30 million dollars in these ranges.

The range itself consists of several major subsystems. These include the physical building itself with airconditioning and RF suppressant material, a stable platform for extreme accuracy, a parabolic reflector, an RF source, the radome mounting and holding fixture, a self test fixture and the system control console. Figure 3 shows the layout of a typical compact test range.

OTHER AUTOMATED TESTERS

There are several other automated testers which will be used by the F-16 at the depot level. They are described below.

Saints

The Singer Automated Inertia/Navigation Test Set (SAINTS) will be used by the F-16 depot primarily to test the Platform, which is the mechanical SRU out of the Inertial Navigation Unit (INU). It was originally developed for the

Figure 3. Typical Radar Antenna/Radome Compact Test Range

AN/ARN-101 which is a navigation update to the F-4. It is typical of ATE in its overall design. Although not involved directly with the SAINTS development effort, more copies of the SAINTS will probably be procured to handle F-16 workload.

Test Stand For Emergency Power Unit (EPU) Turbine

This is an automated test stand developed by Airesearch to test the EPU Turbine. Basically it controls the flow of fuel (Hydrazine) to the turbine and monitors various data points for such things as temperature, pressure, etc. It is controlled by a minicomputer but is not your normal garden variety ATE. This unit is still in the proposal stage.

FACT II

The Flexible Automatic Circuit Tester (FACT II) will be used by the F-16 depot to test various cables and MUX Bus matrices on the F-16. It was developed by Hughes and is already in the AF inventory. Additional copies will be procured to handle F-16 workload. Again, this tester is fairly typical ATE. We have just initiated development of the test programs and ITAs for about 15 F-16 MUX Bus matrices.

AIS

Initial ORLA results indicate that the Avionics Intermediate Shop (AIS) Tester Replacable Units (TRUs - usually PC boards) are reparable candidates. We are conducting studies to determine what tester will be utilized to support repair of these TRUs. Indications are that the AIS itself or some variation thereof will be used for this workload. A decision should be made by the end of this year.

TEST PACKAGE DEVELOPMENT PROCESS

The "Test Package" is defined as the software, the Interface Test Adapter (ITA) and the associated documentation which allows electronic boxes and circuit cards to be tested by ATE. In general, the development of Test Packages is a long, complex, expensive and little understood process. In order to provide timely, cost effective, quality Test Packages for the F-16 we decided to write a Test Package development plan. AF Reg 800-14 provided the basis for this plan with the structure for the Computer Program Development Plan (CPDP). Thus between mid-1977 and this last summer the F-16 Depot Support CPDP was written. It describes in detail the development process for the test software, ITAs and documentation. It delineates the methods by which the AF will have good visibility into the development of test packages through preliminary documentation reviews and meeting attendance. Test package requirements are specified in the CPDP. We believe that by thinking about the process and determining detailed requirements prior to the development effort we will establish the foundation for the development of timely, cost effective, quality test packages.

During the initial F-16 Support Equipment studies we examined various documentation options for test packages. Some sort of Test Requirements Document (TRD), MIL-STD-1519 or equivalent, is required to provide the information to organically support the test programs. Computer Program Development (Part I) Specifications for test software are required by AFR 800-14. The ITA could also have a Development (Part I) Specification. We decided to combine all three of these into one document except where excessive ITA complexity requires a separate specification. This is the System Test Specification (STS) Volume I. It is essentially a MIL-STD-1519 TRD with the test requirements written in ATLAS and some ITA information such as ITA schematics.

In addition to the above, a Computer Program Product (Part II) Specification is required by AFR 800-14. An ITA Product (Part II) Specification could be written. We are preparing an STS Volume II which will contain the source/object listings and references to final ITA drawings. If ITA complexity warrants, a separate ITA Spec will be written.

For ATE control and support (station) software a Computer Program Product Specification is being procured. As we are using existing stations some of this type documentation already exists. We have examined this existing documentation and where it is insufficient to provide AF organic support we are generating new documentation. For instance, we are generating flowcharts and subroutine explanations for all of the Texas Instruments station software. We are also buying Version Description Documents and other Configuration Management aids, and test plans, test reports, ATE users documentation and Technical Orders.

Our experience has shown that from 1 to 3 SRUs of similar stimuli and measurement requirements can cost-effectively utilize a single ITA. For example, the digital station is being used to test approximately 112 SRUs but has only 81 ITAs.

Figure 4 shows the development process for the analog, microwave and non ATPG digital test packages. Figure 5 shows the same information for the ATPG digital test packages. The figures are fairly self-explanatory starting with SERD approval and ending with final selloff to the AF. The CPDP, of course, contains much more detail than these simple figures. Notice, however, that both ITA design and ITA self test development are included. Engineering Evaluation and Test (EET) is that extremely important phase where the ITA, the test program and the tester are brought together for the first time. The only thing guaranteed at this point is that it won't work the first time. A great deal of software/hardware debug and modification occurs during this phase. Notice also that there are two System Compatibility Tests. The AF will generate a list of faults to be inserted into actual SRUs during SCT. After successful SCT completion at GD/FW the Test Package will be shipped to the appropriate ALC. Here SCT will be repeated and a total of 5 different SRUs tested by the Test Packages over the next several months. This way we will be assured of an inplace working system.

Figure 4. Analog, Microwave and non ATPG Digital Test Package Development Process

Figure 5. ATPG Digital Test Package Development Process

There is no good, inexpensive way of determining the quality of Test Packages after they

have been developed. Fault insertion is fine but is prohibitively expensive if extensive enough to actually prove fault detection requirements. The F-16 SPO decided to perform a moderate fault insertion program supplemented with good AF visibility into the development of the Test Packages. The CPDP is structured to provide this visibility. Figures 4 and 5 show how the review of the Preliminary STSs and attendance at GD/FW review meetings will provide this visibility. This process was arrived at by requesting GD/FW to provide their internal test package development and review process. We then decided to request advance copies of STSs and advance notice of the meetings. By participating in the GD/FW process rather than causing them to generate a different process (such as PDRs, CDRs, FCAs and PCAs) just for the AF, we have minimized the negative financial and schedule impacts of such visibility. We then conducted an internal manpower evaluation considering ALC, Air Logistics Division, ASD and independent contractor manpower sources. Due to AF manpower constraints and other considerations the F-16 SPO elected to contract with Technology Development Corporation (TDC) to perform an Independent Assessment of the test packages. Of the 200 A/C SRUs being tested by the three main stations, 190 are out of LRUs whose test programs are currently being Independently Assessed by TDC for the Avionics Intermediate Shop program.

EPROM/PROM CONSIDERATIONS

The F-16 has seven SRUs composed primarily of Erasable Programmable Read Only Memory (EPROM) ICs that are used to store two Operational Flight Programs (OFFPs) of medium volatility. All 7 can be erased and reprogrammed at the SRU level. We analyzed several alternatives for the repair and reprogramming of these seven SRUs. The use of the depot digital station, the AIS at the depot, the AIS in the field and a stand alone eraser/programmer/verifier were all considered. The significant cost driver turned out to be the number of spare SRUs required to fill the pipeline from the depot to the field. Primarily because of the high cost of these spare SRUs it is cheaper to reprogram in the field and repair at the depot. This will also provide Tactical Air Command with the capability to quickly retrofit the fleet with a new OFFP. We are about to initiate development of this stand alone EPROM eraser/programmer/verifier for both field and depot use.

The F-16 has 19 different Programmable Read Only Memory (PROM) ICs on 47 different SRUs. The F-16 is currently planning to spare these PROMs unprogrammed (blank). These PROMs must be programmed prior to insertion into the SRU. We have analyzed various options similar to the EPROM options. We have not yet concluded this study, but all indications point to a stand alone PROM programmer at the depot.

CONFIGURATION MANAGEMENT

Configuration management is a critical

discipline for ATE. It is also one in which our reputation is poor. Horror stories abound of support equipment which does not match the latest aircraft configuration. The F-16 SPO is working hard to correct these problems. All aircraft change traffic must include any support equipment update required. To insure this, all change traffic is routed through both the GD/FW depot ATE engineering office and the F-16 SPO depot ATE office. ATE control and support software is configuration baselined when delivered to GD/FW for test package development. This will improve ATE station software stability. We have established two baselines for test package software. There is an engineering baseline which occurs after the STS Volume I has been reviewed. At this point GD/FW initiates an internal change traffic control and documentation process. After completion of the final SCT at the ALC, the configuration baseline is established. This provides for full configuration control board control. The ATPG system will greatly aid configuration management of digital test programs. Overall, we believe that we have initiated several concepts that will greatly aid in reducing the historic problems the military has seen in the configuration management area.

Warranties covering over 100 SRUs. This may cause SRU change traffic to increase dramatically as the financial incentive to increase avionics reliability is applied. For this and other reasons the task of making the support equipment match the latest aircraft configuration will be difficult. We may or may not implement the Computer Program Identification Number (CPIN) system, a decision we have yet to make. The depot program was added very late to the F-16 development program and so SRU testability is spotty at best. But, as I stated before, these are all actually areas of opportunity and I feel confident that the AF, in cooperation with our industry counterparts, will solve these and many other problems in the future.

FUTURE

As we look to the next several years we see the F-16 depot ATE development program reaching its greatest level of activity between summer of 1979 and summer of 1981. All of the ATE will be delivered to GD/FW between now and the middle of 1979 to support test package development. We have initiated test package development and anticipate first delivery of a test package (and a tester, of course) to the AF by mid-1979. As the test packages and testers arrive we will become organic on more and more aircraft electronic equipment. The entire F-16 Depot ATE program is scheduled to be complete by September 1981 at a cost of approximately \$200M. We anticipate developing the automatic test capability for approximately 200 avionics SRUs, 150-200 AIS TRUs and 100-200 matrices, cables, radomes, turbines and other miscellaneous equipments. We anticipate sufficient workload to justify 10 microwave, 13 analog and 7 digital testers.

We have tried to establish the framework for a successful program. We can, however, see already that there will be plenty of areas of opportunity (called problem areas by negativists) in the future. For one thing, the basic decisions on the locations of the depot repair centers for various F-16 components have been very late and to this date are not complete. The AIS TRU repair location, for example, is still unknown. The use of existing stations has a number of management and technical advantages. Their inherently older technology has, however, proven difficult to support and limited in capability, leading to complex ITAs and ancillary equipment. The use of multiple ATE software systems from multiple ATE vendors is difficult. The F-16 program is utilizing Reliability Improvement